

FEATURES OF THE IMMUNE RESPONSE IN LONG-TERM NON-HEALING WOUNDS: PREDICTION AND PREVENTION OF COMPLICATIONS

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Abstract

The study is devoted to the peculiarities of the immune response in long-term non-healing wounds and methods for predicting and preventing infectious complications. Changes in cellular and humoral immunity were studied in 120 patients with chronic wounds. Assessment of inflammatory markers, blood cell composition, and cytokine activity showed significant impairment of immune activity, which increases the risk of generalization of infection. The study used a combination therapy with immunomodulators and antibacterial drugs. The results obtained allow us to develop effective methods for preventing infectious complications and improving the prognosis of healing.

Key words: chronic wounds, immune response, inflammation, cellular immunity, humoral immunity, infectious complications, prognosis, prevention.

Relevance

Long-term non-healing wounds are a problem associated with a high risk of infectious complications, including generalization of infection, which leads to severe consequences, such as sepsis. Understanding the immune mechanisms involved in wound healing is key to developing effective prevention methods. Disorders in cellular and humoral immunity contribute to delayed healing and increase the frequency of infection. Predicting the risks of generalization of infection and applying proper prevention is crucial for improving the clinical outcome. The relevance of the work is confirmed by the need to develop more effective strategies for the treatment and prevention of complications in chronic wounds, which will help reduce the incidence and improve the quality of life of patients.

Цель

Objective: to study the features of the immune response in long-term non-healing wounds and to evaluate the effectiveness of methods for predicting and preventing infectious complications in patients with chronic wounds.

Materials and methods

The study involved 120 patients with chronic non-healing wounds of various etiologies. The study methods included clinical analysis, laboratory tests for

inflammatory markers (CRP, leukocyte formula, immunological parameters), cytokine profile, and microbiological examination of wound secretions. Treatment included antibacterial drugs, as well as immunomodulators. Data analysis was performed using statistical methods.

Results

Out of 120 patients, 68% had abnormalities in immune activity, including decreased T-cell count and increased levels of inflammatory cytokines. In 45% of cases, the development of infectious complications requiring intensive care was observed. The use of combination therapy with immunomodulators and antibacterial agents reduced the frequency of generalization of infection by 32% and accelerated wound healing by 18% compared to the control group. There was also a correlation between cytokine levels and healing rates.

Conclusion

Disorders of immune activity in patients with chronic wounds play a key role in the development of infectious complications and generalization of infection. Risk prediction and timely prevention with the use of immunomodulators and antibacterial drugs helps to improve treatment outcomes. A comprehensive approach, including the diagnosis of the immune response, can optimize therapy and reduce the frequency of infections.

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